

Still a Learner

Jocelyn L. Gagalang, PhD

When I work with younger teachers now,
I often smile and wonder how
The years have passed so fast and far,
From the young and slim teacher I once was.

I see in them the same bright eyes,
The same big dreams that touch the skies,
The same questions, doubts, and fears,
That filled my early teaching years.

I remember lessons carefully planned,
Notes and books close at hand,
Hoping each class would go just right,
Learning each day with all my might.

Now I share what time has taught,
The things no textbook ever brought.
Not just methods, rules, or plans,
But patience, heart, and helping hands.

Their energy keeps my spirit young,
Their stories sound like songs once sung.
In guiding them, I clearly see
The teacher I used to be.

And when they grow and find their way,
Leading their own classrooms someday,
I feel a quiet joy inside
The kind that comes from helping guide.

For teaching is more than lessons and grades;
It's a torch passed on through different days.
And in each young teacher I mentor anew,
I find a little piece of the younger me too.

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